

artemis

An integrated approach To improve the Environmental performance of smart cities

Report Work Package 1

Data collection, UM modelling and preliminary analysis for the Autonomous Province of Trento

Project acronym	ARTEMIS
Project title	An integrated appRoach To improve the Environmental performMance of smart cltieS
GA no	101026073
Output	Project deliverable 3 (D3) Report Work Package 1 - Data collection, UM modelling and preliminary analysis for the Autonomous Province of Trento
DOI	10.5281/zenodo.7681412
Version	V1.0
Date	22.03.2023
Dissemination Level	Public (PU)
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Acknowledgements

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No. 101026073.

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List of acronyms and abbreviations

APT	Autonomous Province of Trento
CN	Combined nomenclature
CPA	Classification of products by activity
EU	European Union
EW-MFA	Economy-wide material flow accounts
GDP	Gross domestic period
GHG	Greenhouse gas
H2020	Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme
IE	Industrial ecology
ISPAT	Istituto di Statistica della Provincia di Trento (Statistics Institute of the Province of Trento)
ISTAT	Istituto Nazionale di Statistica (National Statistics Institute in Italy)
KPI	Key performance indicator
LCA	Life-Cycle Assessment
MFA	Material Flow Accounting
NACE	Statistical Classification of Economic Activities
NUTS	Nomenclature of Territorial Units for Statistics (Eurostat)
ROC	Rest of the country
UM	Urban Metabolism
UMAn	Urban Metabolism Analyst
UN	United Nations
WP	Work Package

Project abstract

The smart city concept has received increased attention from researchers and decision-makers across the EU. However, there is a gap between smart city research & practice, and environmental sustainability: to date, smart city projects have not adequately assessed the environmental impacts of their strategies, which remain largely unknown. Research is needed to provide empirical evidence, advanced tools and metrics that can support the design, implementation and evaluation of smart city strategies to improve urban environmental sustainability.

Research goals

ARTEMIS will investigate whether and how the smart city can improve the environmental performance of urban systems. The research aims to provide insight on key aspects in smart city strategies that can effectively reduce environmental impacts; a novel environmental impact assessment framework to support decision-making in smart city projects; and improved key performance indicators (KPIs) on environmental sustainability and circularity for smart cities.

Achieving the goals

ARTEMIS will develop an integrated framework coupling urban metabolism and life-cycle assessment, to estimate how strategies implemented in two EU-funded smart city projects (in Lisbon, Portugal, and Trento, Italy) have affected a wide set of environmental impacts, associated with urban systems. Drawing on the framework and results, KPIs will be provided to evaluate environmental sustainability in smart cities. The framework, recommendations and KPIs will be replicable across EU cities.

Relevance to the Work Programme

ARTEMIS will support the EU's vision for smart cities and its aim of becoming a role model in sustainable development. The researcher's expertise in environmental impact assessment and the supervisor's in smart cities bond effectively to pursue the research plan. The fellowship is a unique opportunity for the researcher to obtain enhanced knowledge and skills on the development of environmental assessment tools and metrics for smart cities.

1. Introduction

ARTEMIS aims at developing an integrated framework coupling urban metabolism and life-cycle assessment, to estimate how strategies implemented in EU-funded smart city have affected a wide set of environmental impacts, associated with urban systems. This report summarizes the Urban Metabolism (UM) modelling work performed within the project, including the materials and methods applied (e.g., data collection and processing) and main results. The UM modelling work is directly linked and required to fulfil the project's specific objectives, in particular those of work package 1 (WP1), as outlined in the project proposal: *to quantify the material and product flows associated with urban systems before & after the implementation of smart city strategies*.

The report¹ is structured as follows: section 2 provides the background, including main methodological concepts, such as urban metabolism, the integration of material flow accounting and life-cycle assessment to assess environmental impacts associated with urban areas, the UM model, and a brief description of the case study area (Trento); section 3 describes the materials and methods applied in the UM model; section 4 presents and discusses the results; section 5 provides concluding remarks, including model limitations and improvement opportunities.

2. Background

While covering less than 3% of the world land surface, cities have more than half of the world's population and contribute to about 80% of global economic output, and they concentrate trade, business, innovation and skills [1]. Cities have also been associated with 60-80% of global resource requirements, energy use and anthropogenic greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions [2]. Despite the global and local sustainability challenges associated with increasing urbanization, the concentration of population and economic activities in cities offers unique opportunities, and cities play a key role in climate change mitigation and sustainable development [3–6]. The central role of cities in sustainable development is demonstrated by EU policies and the UN 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, including the Sustainable Development Goals [2]. Urban environmental sustainability, in particular, contributes to four UN Sustainable Development Goals [2], namely: (i) sustainable and just economies; (ii) energy decarbonization with universal access; (iii) urban and peri-urban development; and (iv) global environmental commons.

Industrial ecology tools and approaches can help support the design, development and implementation of sustainable urban development strategies. These include urban metabolism (UM), material flow accounting (MFA) and life-cycle assessment (LCA). Urban metabolism (UM) is widely supported as an approach to inform and support sustainable urban development. In brief, the metabolism of cities comprises the visualization of the city as an organism or ecological system, and it addresses all the socio-economic and environmental processes associated with urban activities. Such system is a network of many components and subsystems (e.g., people, built environment, water, energy, waste, health, transportation) [1]. In this context, UM is in line with the application of a systems thinking approach to provide a broader understanding of urban functions, needs, linkages across different domains, systems and processes, identifying hotspots and opportunities for improvement with an integrated perspective. System theory provides systematic approach for integrating systems, to understand and predict changes within systems, and their implications [1,7]. It also has the potential to address urban complexity, providing insight on the diversity and intensity of urban activities at a multi-scalar level (e.g., from building blocks to neighbourhoods or cities).

¹ Significant portions of this report have been published Bastos, J. and Rosado, L. (2023) Regional metabolism: A material and product flow accounting model for Trentino, Italy. In: Bisello, A. et al. (Eds.) *Smart and Sustainable Planning for Cities and Regions – Results of SSPCR 2022*. Conference Proceedings, Springer (submitted for publication).

Within UM, a commonly used method is Material Flow Accounting (MFA), which considers the inputs of resources (e.g., materials, products, goods) and outputs of emissions and waste, associated with environmental burdens [8]. Despite increasing and remarkable research advances in recent years, UM has limitations that have prevented wider application to assess urban areas and support decision-making. For example, it has high data and resource requirements [9]; the insight on urban material flows (usually in terms of mass) is limiting to support decision-making as it lacks insight on the environmental implications of such flows, and on upstream and downstream processes that occur beyond the city or system boundaries (e.g., extraction, production, transportation, end-of-life) [9]. MFA does not allow an assessment of climate impacts associated with an urban development strategy or policy [3]. Life-cycle assessment (LCA), on the other hand, provides a detailed and systematic quantification of environmental impacts of a system, including upstream and downstream impacts. LCA is an internationally standardized methodology to estimate potential environmental impacts associated with a product, system or service, from cradle-to-grave, i.e., from raw material extraction, to manufacture, transport, use and end-of-life [10]. However, its application to urban areas has been heavily limited by its large time and data requirements.

The application of industrial ecology tools to urban areas has been increasing, as they can support more holistic, systematic and integrated assessment of complex systems, helping to identify burden-shifts and undesirable consequences and trade-offs; however, there is room to improve their integration and application for evaluating the environmental performance of urban areas. This report presents an UM MFA-based model that was specifically developed for future integration with LCA.

2.1. Material flow accounts and indicators

Physical accounting approaches are important to complement monetary approaches which are generally insufficient (and at times inadequate) to describe the relationship between the economy and the environment and, ultimately, between humans and their habitat. For over 20 years, the UN has called for an integration of environmental and economic accounting, by quantifying services provided by natural capital as well as human-made capital. This is essential to characterize and manage the use and/or depletion of natural resources (in production to consumption chains) and the associated environmental implications [11]. MFA can serve as a basis for environmental monitoring and management of urban areas – accounting and characterizing material and product flows to evaluate their environmental impacts [12, p.12]. MFA relies on the principle of mass balance, where total material inputs (entries) into a system must equal total outputs plus the net accumulation within the system [12, p.12]. The principle of mass balance applies to the economy as a whole, but also to any of its subsystems (economy sectors, companies, etc.) [12, p.12].

Economy-wide material flow accounts (EW-MFA) are a statistical accounting framework applied at national level in the EU to report, in thousand tonnes per year, material flows into and out of an economy. The general purpose of EW-MFA is to describe the physical interaction of a national economy with the natural environment and the rest of the world economy in terms of flows of materials (covering solid, gaseous, and liquid materials, except for bulk flows of water and air). In 2011, the EU regulation No. 691/2011 implemented a legal obligation for EU Member States to report the EW-MFA to Eurostat; and in 2013, mandatory annual data collection and reporting started. Eurostat published a methodological guide for EW-MFA [13] and its derived indicators, including overall material flow balances and aggregated indicators on total resource requirements, resource efficiency and total domestic outflows to the environment. In 2012, the System of Environmental-Economic Accounting - Central Framework (SEEA-CF) was adopted as an international statistical standard by the UN [14], including a section on EW-MFA, which supports the need and appropriateness of EW-MFA for accounting and reporting material flows.

2.2. The UMAN model

Remarkable research advances have been made in recent years that improved the application of UM and MFA to regional and urban areas, supporting a holistic, systematic and integrated analysis of such complex systems, and providing important insights on resource use and efficiency. As mentioned, however, there is room for improvement, in particular by increasing the level of detail of UM and MFA models. Further insight, for example, on the specific use of materials is important to evaluate the potential environmental impacts associated with resource flows. An important advancement has been made by the Urban Metabolism Analyst (UMAn) model, which provides a methodological framework to account for material and product flows and stocks at regional and urban levels, building on the EW-MFA methodology [15]. The framework contributed to advancing UM research, for example, by:

- Contributing to a more systematic and harmonized methodology, particularly suitable for EU regions and cities, as it builds on EW-MFA and builds on Eurostat standard statistical data for products (complemented with other datasets and sources);
- Assigning product composition to 28 harmonized material types, increasing disaggregation/categorization level of material types;
- Disaggregating data by economic sector and characterizing the life-cycle phase of products, providing insight on the origin and destination of flows; and
- Including information about product lifespan to provide understanding on the dynamics of added stock (e.g., the potential that stocks may have in the recovery of resources).

2.3. Case study: The Autonomous Province of Trento

The Autonomous Province of Trento is located in Northern Italy (Figure 1). In 2020, the province population was 542 166 [16], registering a 13% increase over the last 20 years [17]. About 22% of the population lives in the province capital city, Trento [18]. The province has a relatively high quality of life: GDP in 2020 was 37 120€/cap in the province, compared to a national GDP of 27 938€/cap [19]. The province is located in the Italian Alps, in the Dolomites, thus characterized by a mountainous territorial morphology; and the provincial economy relies strongly on tourism and manufacturing sectors.

Fig. 1 – Case study: the Autonomous Province of Trento, in Italy.

3. Materials and methods

This section summarizes the materials and methods used in the UM model, including sources, input datasets, data analysis and processing. It is structured in four subsections, which draw on the four steps of EW-MFA:

- 3.1) System boundaries;
- 3.2) Data compilation and processing;
- 3.3) Data analysis and classification of products; and
- 3.4) Calculation of indicators.

The research project aims for the highest possible level of transparency, reproducibility and replicability of data and results generated. As such, the selection of materials and methods has been oriented to ensure replicability and scalability. The research findings, data and results are applicable to other projects, geographical areas and urban systems, to support the design, implementation and evaluation of urban development strategies.

3.1. System boundaries

National, regional and urban MFAs can be defined by two types of boundaries: one is the boundary between the economy and natural environment (cross-border flows that consist of inputs and outputs environment-economy, such as domestic extraction); and the second is the border with other economies (cross border flows that consist, for example, of imports and exports) [12, p.22]. Both types of boundaries need to be clearly defined to ensure consistent accounting of material flows. Borders with other economies are generally associated with geographic boundaries. These often correspond to administrative units, which are particularly important since the model strongly depends on the type, quality and disaggregation of available data that can be collected for specific administrative units/levels.

Fig. 2 – Simplified structure and scope of the UM model: regional material flow accounting.

A simplified structure and scope of the UM model is presented in Figure 2. In brief, borders between the economy and natural environment in the model were associated with domestic extraction flows (inputs), namely: animal breeding and slaughtering, forestry activities (wood harvesting), fishing and aquaculture, the production of milk, milk products and eggs, mining and quarrying; and waste (outputs). While geographic borders were applied to consider inputs and outputs from and to other economies (imports and exports). Geographic borders considered the administrative borders of the Autonomous Province of Trento, which correspond to a NUTS3² territorial unit (code ITH20), and of the municipality of Trento, which corresponds to a local territorial unit (code 022205).

3.2. Data compilation and treatment

Figure 3 summarises the general structure of the UM model developed, and main data sources used, drawing on the UMAN model structure and plugin data. In brief, data to calculate and characterize material and product flows was collected, using 2019 as the reference year (the most recent year before the Covid-19 crisis in Italy), and compiled into:

- Main tables (international trade, industrial production, transport of goods and domestic extraction);
- Correspondence tables (e.g., between product classification systems); and
- Support tables (employees, residents).

The different types of tables and data compilation are described next. Further details are provided in Appendix I.

Main Tables

These tables have statistical data on material flows. Four main tables were compiled: Domestic Extraction, International Trade, Transport of Goods and Industrial Production.

Domestic Extraction – the domestic extraction table compiles data from seven sectors or groups: (a) mining and quarrying, (b) agricultural production, (c) wood harvesting (forestry), (d) fishing and aquaculture, (e) meat, (f) milk products, and (g) eggs. These came from a range of national and regional datasets on extraction and primary production. When data at regional/province level was not available it was allocated based on number of employees in the respective sector. Data was collected from the national and regional statistics office databases, ISTAT and ISPAT, respectively [18,19], and compiled according to the Combined Nomenclature (CN) classification system, which is the main classification for the European international trade in good statistics used by Eurostat. Data was collected for Italy, the Autonomous Province of Trento and Trento municipality.

International Trade – international trade is reported at national level with CN structure - an allocation was done on the volume of international imports that go to the modelled region and that of international imports that go to the rest of the country (ROC), and the same was done for exports (disaggregating them into exports from the province and from the ROC). To do so, international trade data was combined with data on the economic sectors of destination of imports and of origin of exports, and with data on the significance of economic sectors in the province and in the ROC, in terms of number of employees per economic sector (support table).

² Nomenclature of Territorial Units for Statistics (NUTS), Eurostat.

Inter-regional Trade – to apply MFA to regions and cities, we need to account for national imports and exports, i.e., flows from the ROC to the modelled region, and from the modelled region to the ROC. The model used national annual road freight transport by regions of loading and unloading and by group of goods from Eurostat, structured with the Standard Goods Classification [20]. Rail was assumed to account for 26% of the overall inter-regional trade, based on a report on the transport of goods across the Brennero axis [21]. Water and air transport were excluded, due to the specificities of the region (no seaports nor major airports exist in the province). The Standard Goods Classification for Transport Statistics (NST2007) provides statistical information about flows of products between NUTS2 units, based on their economic activity of origin. It is available for four modes of transport: road; rail; air; and water.

Industrial Production – data on manufactured goods by industrial sector was used to model product transformation, i.e., the processing of raw materials and intermediate products into final products for consumption. Industrial production data is available at national level [18], in ProdCom NACE Rev 2 categories. Harmonization was needed on several product units, to convert non mass units into mass (in tonnes), which was based on the Eurostat Conversion Factors Table (with information on the average weight of several Combined Nomenclature Codes that are not accounted in mass weight). For products that were not in the Eurostat conversion factors table, conversion factors were selected from the literature (bibliographic and desk research). Data was collected for Italy, the Autonomous Province of Trento and Trento municipality.

Fig. 3 – UM model: main structure and data tables (adapted from: [15])

Fs = Forestry statistics; QMs = quarry and mining statistics; AGs = agriculture statistics; Fls = Fishing and aquaculture statistics; Workers = number of workers; Residents = resident population; MatCat = Material Categories; Phase = Life-cycle stage.

Correspondence Tables

These tables have correspondences across classification systems, and they build mostly on the Reference and Management of Nomenclatures system of Eurostat, RAMON.

CN, CPA and NACE – These tables provide the correspondence between CN and EU Classification of Products by Activity (CPA) codes and Statistical Classification of Economic Activities (NACE), made available by Eurostat. CPA follows the production origin criterion, i.e., products are grouped according to the economic activity of origin. NACE first revision (Rev. 1.1) is from 2002, second revision is from 2008 (Rev. 2).

NST to CN – National and international transport data can be available in different disaggregation levels and nomenclature. The most common is the Standard Goods Classification for transport statistics (NST or NSTR, depending on the year), which was linked in this table to the respective CN2 codes.

CN correspondences – the database developed to support the UMaN model was built according to CN2007 codes. As such, a correspondence table was built drawing on the yearly correspondence tables available in Eurostat RAMON website, between CN2007 and CN2019 (model reference year).

Support Tables

These tables drew on ISTAT data [18], and they were mainly used to support extrapolations when province or municipality specific data were not available.

Employees – number of employees by NACE 2007 code by municipality was considered, from ISTAT data on enterprises – number of persons employed of local units of active enterprises (annual average values) 2019.

Residents – number of residents by municipality, to allocate goods for final household consumption in the city of Trento.

3.2.1. UMaN model plugins

The model used three datasets previously developed as UMaN model plugins [12, p.80]:

- Lifecycle: a dataset assigning a stage according to the life-cycle phase of products, which was used to separate final and intermediate products in input flows (to model product transformation);
- MatCat: a dataset assigning the main materials in products' composition; and
- Lifespan: a dataset with the average lifespan (or service life) of products, which was used to estimate additions to stock (by identifying products with average lifespan larger than 1 year).

These databases were built for CN2007 product types, used by Eurostat in International Trade Statistics.

Lifecycle

The lifecycle dataset consists of a matrix that disaggregates CN codes into intermediate and final products. This was used to then model product transformation (of intermediate products) in the region, exports of processed/transformed goods, and the consumption of final products.

MatCat

MatCat is a matrix of main material composition of CN2007 product types, which assigns product shares to 28 material groups, presented in Table 1.

Table 1 – Material groups considered in the UMAN model plugin MatCat.

Fossil Fuels (FF)	FF1	Fuels
	FF2	Other fossil fuels
	FF3	Lubricants and oils and solvents
	FF4	Plastics and rubbers
Metals (MM)	MM1	Iron, steel alloying metals and ferrous metals
	MM2	Light metals
	MM3	Non-ferrous heavy metals
	MM4	Special metals
	MM5	Nuclear fuels
	MM6	Precious metals
Non-metallic minerals (NM)	NM1	Sand
	NM2	Cement
	NM3	Clay
	NM4	Stone
	NM5	Other (Fibres, salt, inorganic parts of animals)
Biomass (forestry, crops & animal products) (BM)	BM1	Agricultural biomass
	BM2	Animal biomass
	BM3	Textile biomass
	BM4	Oils & fats
	BM5	Sugars
	BM6	Wood and fuels
	BM7	Paper & board
	BM8	Non-specified biomass
Chemicals & fertilizers (CF)	CF1	Alcohols
	CF2	Chemicals and pharmaceuticals
	CF3	Fertilizers and pesticides
Others (O)	O1	Non-specified
	O2	Liquids

Lifespan

This dataset can be important to address the throughput of products, accumulation of stock and future waste generation, for example. Our model is for a one-year analysis – the trends over time, waste generation, etc. are beyond the main focus of the analysis. As such, we considered only whether the lifespan is ≤ 1 year, i.e., consumed within 1 year, or longer, i.e., added to the stock.

3.3. Data analysis and classification of products

With the data collected and treated as described, we:

- calculated domestic material inputs to the region (domestic extraction + imports) and estimated overall available resources (preliminary material balance);
- characterized inputs (available resources) splitting them into intermediate and final products;
- modelled product transformation in the region (transformation of intermediate products into final products, for consumption in economic sectors or final household consumption);
- calculated amount of products available for final consumptions (domestic material consumption). Classification of products by predominant material type (into 28 material types); and
- characterised material composition of products.

3.3.1. Product transformation

First, an adjustment was made to balance available resource and exports in CN2 categories that had significant negative balance associated with products that were not outputs of industrial production (and thus not produced in the region to be exported). This consisted of re-assigning exports of critical products (with particularly high negative balance) to similar products that had large volumes of available resources.

- In CN section 22, 50% of grape must (2204 30 10) exports were moved to wine and wine must product types – CN2007 codes 2204 21 67, 2204 21 79 and 2204 21 80 – proportionally to the available resources among the three.
- In CN section 25, 90% of exports of quicklime (2522 10 00), hydraulic lime (2522 30 00) and limestone flux (2521 00 00) were moved to pebbles and gravel for concrete aggregates (2517 10 10), broken/crushed dolomite and limestone flux (2517 10 20) and broken or crushed stone for concrete aggregates (2517 10 80), proportionally to their respective available resource volume; and 90% of exports of ecaussine and other calcareous stone (2515 20 00) were moved to crushed dolomite (2518 10 00).
- In CN section 44, 50% of exports of coniferous wood chips or particles (4401 21 00) were moved to coniferous wood in the rough (4403 20 99).
- In CN section 68, 50% of exports from articles of stone containing magnesite, dolomite or chromite (6815 91 00) were moved to hand sharpening or polishing stones (6805 30 10).

Then, product transformation consisted essentially of a step to iteratively model processing of intermediate goods in the region and associating the outputs of transformation to exports. First, exports were taken from intermediate and final products that resulted from domestic extraction in the region (DE – exports). Second, the remaining available resources (remaining DE + imports) were divided into intermediate and final products (using ProdChar, as described in 3.2.1). Third, the transformation of intermediate products considered an Industrial production matrix, that linked the intermediate products that served as inputs to a NACE sector, to that sector's outputs products, and to the volume of waste generated by that same sector. These linkages built on supply and use tables for Italy (with 63 product types and 63 sectors, at base price) and on waste generation data by NACE sector for Italy. After two loops of product transformation (i.e., intermediate products that came out of the first output went into a second product transformation loop), another adjustment was made to balance inputs and outputs of the region, transferring among CN2 groups of categories that had the same main materials from CN2 categories with negative balance to those with positive balance, proportionally. Lastly, the final balancing step was to remove the remaining exports that could not be matched by specific product types proportionally, from all available product types in the region.

3.4. Calculation of indicators

With the domestic extraction (DE), Imports and Exports, we calculated the direct material input (DMI), as described in Eq. (1). Then, the transformation of intermediate products into final products was modelled, based on industrial production data. Domestic material consumption (DMC) was then calculated with the final products (DMI_f) (which excluded waste generated in the product transformation), as described in Eq. (2). Lastly, to downscale DMC to the province’s capital city Trento, the “Use table” of CPA products by NACE sector was considered (for service sectors using predominantly final products) and the relative share of employees by NACE sector in the municipality of Trento and in the Province; and the share of residents in the case of use of the CPA products for final consumption (by households, social support organizations and public administration).

$$DE + Imports = DMI \tag{1}$$

$$DMI_f - Exports = DMC \tag{2}$$

4. Results and discussion

In this section we summarize key results of the MFA model application to the Autonomous Province of Trento, including available resources (preliminary material balance), domestic material inputs (DMI) and domestic material consumption (DMC), together with the DMC of its capital city, Trento.

4.1. Available resources

Figure 4 illustrates the available resources modelled by CN2019 section, including domestic extraction, national and international imports, and national and international exports. These represent the inputs and outputs considered in the model, and they present model results with the lowest level of uncertainty, before significant extrapolations were made on product transformation. The overall balance between inputs and outputs resulted in a total estimate of 6 866 345 tonnes of consumed material resources (incl. waste) in the province.

Fig. 4 – Available resources by CN section (preliminary material balance).

Most flows were associated with inter-regional trade: only 6 and 9% of the overall exports and imports were international, respectively. Section V on mineral products, was significant in all types of flows, except for international exports: it accounted for 66% of domestic extraction, 27% of national imports and 25% of national exports. Two other sections showed to be particularly relevant: section IX on wood and articles of wood, and section X on pulp of wood and paper products. The first accounted for 13-19% of all types of flows; while the second accounted for 9-18% of imports and 6-13% of exports (no domestic extraction). Lastly, exports were always lower than the respective imports – national and international – however, in international trade exports were 62% lower, while in national trade only 4%.

4.2. Direct material inputs

Direct material inputs (DMI) to the province in 2019 were 28 499 thousand tonnes, of which 52% were final products. Figure 5 shows the composition of inputs for final and intermediate products by CN2019 section. Three CN sections were particularly relevant in both types of inputs – intermediate and final products: II on vegetable products (these accounted for 8% of intermediate products and 12% of final products); V on mineral products (32-35%) and IX on wood and articles of wood (13-19%). Sections IV, VI and XIII were significant inputs that entered the province mostly as final products, corresponding to prepared food and vegetables, chemical products and articles of stone, plaster and cement, respectively. These CN sections accounted for 7, 14 and 9% of the final product inputs, respectively. Lastly, two sections had significant inputs that consisted primarily of intermediate products, for processing/transformation in the province: X on pulp of wood and paper products, and XV on base metals, accounting for 14 and 11% of the intermediate product inputs, respectively.

Fig. 5 – Composition of direct material inputs (DMI): intermediate and final products.

Figure 6 shows the material composition of direct material inputs (DMI) for 28 types of materials. Non-metallic minerals and biomass accounted for over 77% of the material inputs. This is closely linked with the results observed in the preliminary material balance, where sections V, IX and X on mineral products, wood products and wood pulp and paper products were particularly significant. Within non-metallic mineral products, inputs were mostly composed by stone and sand; while in biomass, wood and biofuels, agricultural biomass, and paper, accounted for most inputs.

In product transformation from intermediate to final products, 5.5 million tonnes of intermediate products were transformed in a first loop and about 2.1 million in a second loop, generating around 700 thousand tonnes of waste. It is important to highlight, however, that any other waste generated in the province was not considered in our model, such as household waste and waste from construction activities, which are expected to account for most of the generated waste.

Fig. 6 – Material composition of direct material inputs (DMI).

4.3. Domestic material consumption

Table 2 presents the domestic material consumption (DMC), and Figure 7 shows the DMC distribution by CN section, in the Autonomous Province of Trento (APT) and in its capital city, Trento. The overall DMC was 11.4 and 12.5 t per capita in the province and in Trento, respectively; the result is below the EU mean of 14.2, but significantly higher than the reported DMC for Italy in the same year of 8.3 t [20].

Table 2 – Domestic material consumption (DMC).

	APT	Trento
Overall DMC (tonnes)	6 219 387	1 495 311
Population (source: [13])	543 721	119 616
DMC per capita (tonnes/cap)	11.44	12.50

APT – Autonomous Province of Trento

The overall DMC per capita results were relatively similar in the province, and in Trento. In 2019, Trento had 22% of the province’s population; the DMC across CN sections varied between 20% in section XIII and 34% in section XVIII, which correspond to Articles of stone, plaster and cement and Instruments, respectively.

Fig. 7 – Domestic material consumption (DMC) in the Autonomous Province of Trento (outer circle) and in the city of Trento (inner circle), for 2019.

5. Concluding remarks

This report summarizes the data, methodology and preliminary results of the UM model developed for the Autonomous Province of Trento and its capital city, Trento, within WP1 of ARTEMIS project. The application of a state-of-the-art methodology, the UMAN model, provided a detailed, systematic and comprehensive estimate of material and product flows and consumption at a regional and urban level.

The UM model is a first component of the environmental impact framework that will be developed, coupling UM and LCA. The next steps in the project will mainly comprise the integration of the UM model with LCA, to develop an environmental impact assessment framework that can estimate the overall environmental impacts of regional and/or urban consumption (yearly). First, representative products of the regional and urban DMC will be selected. Second, water and electricity use in the region and in the city in 2019 will be added to the model. Third, urban consumption will be analysed and classified according to the respective urban sub-system (e.g., buildings/built environment, energy, waste, water, transportation, household consumption/goods and urban green). Lastly, life-cycle environmental impacts of the overall region and city and the relative contributions of the different sub-systems will be calculated.

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Appendix I – Data collection and treatment

<p>Domestic Extraction</p>	<p>(a) Mining - I.Stat data on extraction of mineral resources for 2019 (quarrying and mining, in tonnes). When data was not disaggregated at the Province level, the number of employees in mining and quarrying was used to estimate the APT's respective extraction volume.</p> <p>(b) Agricultural production – ISTAT dataset on Agricultural production by crops (at Province and at national level) in 2019 – total production was used; three categories (primary crops, fodder and wine), removed repetitions and converted wine from hectolitres to tonnes with a 0.98 kg/l factor, removed grapes (except for table grapes) as there was wine. Flowers were excluded.</p> <p>(c) Wood harvesting – ISTAT survey on felling surfaces and wood and not wood removals from forest at Province level, for 2015 (most recent year) in cubic meters. Conversion from cubic meters to tonnes was done with the following factors (m³/t): Fuelwood 1.38; Coniferous: Industrial roundwood (wood in the rough, softwood) 1.43; Non-coniferous: Industrial roundwood (wood in the rough, hardwood) 1.25. Source: https://www.forestresearch.gov.uk/tools-and-resources/statistics/forestry-statistics/forestry-statistics-2018/sources/timber-2/conversion-factors/</p> <p>(d) Fishing & aquaculture – dataset from ISPRA on Produzione d'aquacultura per region for 2018 was used. It had production for Trentino Alto Adige (allocated to the APT based on number of employees), crossed checked with data on production of trout in Trentino. All fish production in the APT was assumed to be trout. At national level fishing was added to the aquaculture production, based on ISTAT dataset on Fishery products in the Mediterranean Sea, also for 2018. Sources: Production of trout in Trentino 2019 – Produzione lorda vendibile della troicoltura per specie (https://statweb.provincia.tn.it/annuario/(S(hxuqss4501pwjrvqopknn455))/tavola.aspx?id=5.09&t=plv). Employees in Ateco 102 ("processing and preserving of fish") and Ateco 46381 ("commerce of fresh fish") in the APT were 84% of the total for Trentino Alto Adige. This factor was applied to estimate fish from aquaculture in Trentino.</p> <p>(e) Meat production – ISTAT dataset on meat slaughtering in Italy and at Province level for 2019. We used mass volume of live weight (there was also dead weight).</p> <p>(f) Milk products – ISTAT dataset on dairy production – data at national is available for more recent years but for the APT only until 2016, so that year was used.</p> <p>(g) Eggs – ISPAT report on agricultural production had number of eggs in APT produced for consumption and hatching – we converted to mass with 60g/egg. Report Ismea for Italy 2018 on eggs for consumption, then eggs for hatching were estimated based on ratio consumption/hatching in Trentino</p>
<p>Industrial Production</p>	<p>Collected dataset Industrial production at national level downloaded from ISTAT (Correspondence Table Prodcom categories to CN2019) Disaggregation into APT and ROC done based on number of persons employed of local units of active enterprises annual average values – support Tables - using 4 left digits of ProdCom NACE Rev 2 categories which identify economic sector.</p> <p>Drawing on the use table we calculate the relative share of a product category that goes into each economic sector, for transformation. Sections A and B of NACE sectors were excluded, because no manufacturing/processing activities are foreseen in these sectors of products coming from other sectors. As such, any products going into these sectors are assumed to be final (e.g., fuel), and not going to be transformed within the sectors.</p> <p>Section A (NACE 1) consists of: Agricultural activities excluding any subsequent processing of the agricultural products (classified under divisions 10 and 11 (Manufacture of food products and beverages) and division 12 (Manufacture of tobacco products)), beyond processing needed to prepare them for the primary markets. The preparation of products for the primary markets is included here. Section B (NACE 5 to 9) states: This section includes supplementary activities aimed at preparing the crude materials for marketing, for example, crushing, grinding, cleaning, drying, sorting, concentrating ores, liquefaction of natural gas and agglomeration of solid fuels. These operations are often accomplished by the units that extracted the resource and/or others located nearby. Also sectors from section G were excluded: This section includes wholesale and retail sale (i.e., sale without transformation) of any type of goods, and rendering services incidental to the sale of merchandise. Wholesaling and retailing are the final steps in the distribution of merchandise. Also included in this section are the repair of motor vehicles and motorcycles.</p> <p>V33 was excluded because there was no industrial production (IP) coming out of this sector. V38 only has two IP outputs – of products composed by metals – as such, we only considered possible inputs those from R24 Metals; M28 Machinery; and M29 Vehicles.</p> <p>Lastly, we excluded section F on the construction of buildings, to be consistent with the model's classification of final products. We consider final products to be at "last gate" – out of the last industrial infrastructure. So, transformation in households or construction sites, does not count as "processing of intermediate products".</p>
<p>International Trade</p>	<p>We have international trade at national level in CN8. For imports this is done using the relative „importance“ (APT/IT) of the economic sector of destination of international imports. For exports we don't know the sector of origin, and use the availability of products for exporting (DE + IP + Nat. imports).</p> <p><u>Imports:</u> To estimate international imports to the APT by NST category (for 13 categories), we use a regional dataset with economic volume of international imports from ISTAT (Importazioni ed esportazioni per attività economica - Trento – 2019) and convert to mass using factor mass/economic volume of international trade at Italian (national) level, and to the respective NST categories.</p> <p>Then, we use IO data on International imports at national (IT) (https://www.istat.it/it/archivio/253253) and regional level (APT) (ISPAT email) to link imported products (63 CPA categories) with the economic sector of destination (63 sectors + final consumption). We use the IO volume of imports to the APT (IO regional table) and to Italy (IO national table) to allocate the imports of products to the APT (CN data on international imports to Italy), according</p>

	<p>to the relative significance of the sectors' imports to the APT and Italy, respectively. Lastly, we adjust the volume of the products to the initial NST imports estimated.</p> <p><u>Exports:</u> International exports from APT used DE + IP + National imports to the APT (which express the availability of resources in the region). Data was only available for NST categories 1 to 14 (no need to distribute unknown products, categories 15 or 17. The only exceptions were NST 7 and 14 which used (14) data on waste generation by NACE sector at national level (allocation to APT based on employees and residents for household (HH) waste) and (7) exports from Italy – international trade, instead of DE + IP + National Imports.</p>
Inter-regional Trade	<p>National imports and exports by NST: Imported goods arrive by rail or road. Transport of goods to and from the APT was only available by NST category for road. We used the National annual road freight transport by regions of loading and unloading (NUTS 3) and by group of goods (in thousand tonnes) from Eurostat, for 2019. Rail transportation was assumed to be 26% of the overall inter-regional trade, based on a report that state that was the share transported by train in the Brennero axis, in terms of mass. Water and air transportation were excluded, due to the specificities of the region (no seaports or major airports exist in the APT). (There is a pipeline, but fuels are assumed to be modelled in the international trade.)</p> <p><u>Exports disaggregation of NST exports to CN8</u> used DE + IP + Int imports APT (which express the availability of resources in the region). Excluded NST categories: 15 – Mail (less than 0.5 of national NST imports) and 17 – moved goods/bags (data was not available). NST 16 – Equipment for transport of goods - was allocated manually to CN 8609 00 90 – Containers. NST 14 - Secondary raw materials/waste disaggregation and NST 7 on Coke and refined petroleum products was done based on (14) data on waste generation by NACE sector at national level (allocation to APT based on employees and residents for HH waste) and (7) exports from Italy – international trade – These two categories could only be disaggregated with „int imports data“ which was assumed not to be representative. Unknown products added – NST categories 18, 19 and 20 were distributed proportionally to CN codes after excluding wood and wood/cork products, sand, stone, gravel, metal and non-ferrous ores, crude oil and oil products (see remarks below). The following CN2 categories were added to the exclusions on the distribution of unknown products because they had a significant negative balance (in the preliminary material balance that estimated available resources in the region), which would be aggravated by increased exports: 02, 04, 20, 48, 72, 86.</p> <p><u>Imports disaggregation of NST imports to CN8 used:</u> we used IO data on International imports at national (IT) (https://www.istat.it/it/archivio/253253) level to link imported products (63 CPA categories) with the economic sector of destination (63 sectors + final consumption) – same data used in Int imports. Then, we considered the volume of DE + IP + International Imports of ROC 2019 in CN8 and distribute to the economic sectors. We splitted each the products to APT and ROC according to significance of the economic sector of destination (shares APT/ROC). Categories 7, 14, 15, 16, 18, 19, 20 treated with the same methodology as exports disaggregation.</p>
Other aspects and remarks	<p><i>Cross flows</i> were assumed to be negligible/not significant in the case of the APT, due to the region characteristics.</p> <p><i>Unknown products</i> – In imports and exports, when using transport of goods data, we need to treat NST categories 18, 19 and 20, which correspond to mixed goods transported together, unidentifiable goods and other goods n.e.c. These were distributed proportionally by CN products in other NST categories (according to the known volume of imports and exports), excluding (list at CN4 in appendix?):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Products of forestry and logging • Products of wood and Cork (excluding furniture) • Crude Oil • Oil Products • Iron ores, Iron and Steel • Non Ferrous Ores • Stone, sand and Gravel <p>It was considered that the previous groups of goods are not part of the unknown values because they are usually transported in large (identified) quantities, and therefore we assume that every time that are transported, they have to be properly registered in the statistics, and not as unknown goods. If the previous goods were considered, they would be a large part of the unknown goods.</p>

Support Tables

Employees	Dataset collected from ISTAT: Enterprises – number of persons employed of local units of active enterprises (annual average values) 2019, in Nace 2007 (Agriculture, Forestry and Aquaculture were added in the table).
Residents	Dataset from I.Stat on resident population on January 1 st , 2019, at municipality level.

